

Mapping Research Topics of Determinants and Influence of Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR) in Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review

Eka Wahyu Hestya Budianto, Nindi Dwi Tetria Dewi
Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang
wahyu.ala@uin-malang.ac.id

Abstract: Using the Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR) ratio is important in making bank strategic decisions, such as setting credit growth targets, debt restructuring, and determining dividend policies. This study aims to determine the research mapping regarding the Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR) ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking using a mix-method approach, namely the VOSviewer bibliometric study and literature review. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the DAR ratio; (2) mapping the results of the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization around the DAR ratio based on the number of clusters and their items; and (3) mapping research topics around the DAR ratio using a literature review study. The results showed that: (1) based on the distribution of journal publications, there were 235 journal publications regarding the DAR ratio; (2) based on the mapping of the VOSviewer bibliometric study, the network visualization results around the DAR ratio are divided into 6 clusters and 171 topic items; (3) based on the mapping of literature review studies, there are 28 topics around the influence of the DAR ratio and 12 topics about the determinants of the DAR ratio. The implications and contributions of this research are to map research topics around DAR ratios in Islamic and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers so that they can be a reference for subsequent researchers.

Keywords: Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR), Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Literature Review, Islamic and Conventional Banking

Introduction

In the banking sector, Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR) is an important indicator used to measure a bank's financial health. Banks tend to have higher DAR ratios than companies in other sectors because of the characteristics of the banking business which requires leverage or debt to make a profit. However, a ratio that is too high can also indicate that the bank has high credit risk and is likely to experience financial difficulties. In addition, the use of DAR in the banking sector is increasingly important due to increasingly higher credit risks. In the banking business, credit risk is one of the main risks that must be managed well. Banks must pay attention to the quality of credit provided and ensure that their credit portfolio is not taken up too much by debtors who have a high risk of default. DAR is an important indicator in this case because the higher the debt ratio, the higher the risk of default that may occur. Apart from that, the use of the DAR ratio is also increasingly developing within the scope of regulations. Several supervisory authorities such as Bank Indonesia and the Financial Services Authority (OJK) require banks to meet certain DAR ratio requirements as part of efforts to maintain financial system stability. This is done to ensure that the bank has a healthy debt level and is able to pay its financial obligations well.

The use of DAR is also increasingly important in making strategic bank decisions, such as determining credit growth targets, debt restructuring and determining dividend policy. Banks must consider their debt ratios in this case to ensure that the decisions taken do not pose too high a risk to the bank's financial health. In conclusion, the use of the DAR ratio in banking is increasingly important

and growing along with the complexity of the banking business and the role of regulation in maintaining financial system stability. Banks must pay attention to this ratio in making strategic decisions and ensure that their debt ratio remains healthy and can be managed well. Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR) or Debt to Asset Ratio is a financial ratio used to measure how much debt a company has compared to the total assets it owns. In banking, DAR refers to the ratio between total debt and total bank assets. By calculating DAR, investors or creditors can assess the level of bank dependence on debt to finance its operations. The higher the DAR ratio, the greater the risk faced by the bank because the greater the portion of bank assets that must be used to pay debts. Conversely, the lower the DAR ratio, the safer the bank's finances because more assets are available to cover debt. In general, banks have a fairly high DAR because banks need a source of funds to lend money to customers and make profits from loan interest. However, a DAR that is too high can be a sign that the bank is in poor financial condition and faces greater risks. Therefore, DAR needs to be considered together with other financial ratios when analyzing a bank's financial health.

Bibliometric studies are research methods that utilize bibliographic data and quantitative measurements to produce information about a particular field or topic. Bibliometric studies are often used to analyze research developments and trends, identify the most influential journals or authors in a particular field, and study the interrelationships between topics or disciplines. Bibliometric methods involve collecting bibliographic data from specific sources, such as scientific journals, research databases, and other scientific works. This data is then analyzed using statistical and mathematical techniques to produce information about the number of publications, number of citations, and relationships between topics or disciplines. In the academic world, bibliometric studies are very useful for evaluating the quality and impact of scientific publications, as well as for identifying new and emerging research trends. Bibliometric studies can also help researchers to identify the most appropriate journals to publish their research, as well as to gain insight into rapidly developing topics or scientific disciplines. However, bibliometric studies also have limitations, especially in terms of collecting accurate and representative bibliographic data. Therefore, the results of bibliometric studies need to be considered carefully and treated as an additional source of information in carrying out analysis and decision making. VOSviewer is network analysis and visualization software that can be used to analyze and visualize patterns in bibliometric data. The software was developed by Nees Jan van Eck and Ludo Waltman of Delft University of Technology in the Netherlands. VOSviewer allows users to visualize the network of connections between bibliographic items, such as journal articles, authors, keywords, or research topics, in graphical form. These graphs can help users to identify patterns and trends in bibliometric data, such as relationships between topics or authors, and allow them to explore the data further. VOSviewer also provides various network analysis features that can be used to examine networks of connections in bibliometric data. These features include cluster analysis, similarity analysis, and centrality analysis, which can help users to identify patterns and relationships in bibliometric data. VOSviewer can be used to analyze bibliometric data from various sources, such as scientific publication databases such as Scopus or Web of Science. This software is widely used in academic research, especially in the social sciences and humanities, to visualize and analyze patterns in bibliometric data.

Studies Literature review is a research method carried out to investigate, analyze and reconstruct existing literature in a particular field or topic. Literature review studies allow researchers to collect and examine information from a variety of relevant sources, such as journal articles, books, reports, and other documents, and then analyze and synthesize that information. Literature review studies aim to

understand what is known and understood about a particular topic, as well as identifying research gaps that still need further research. In this way, literature review studies can help researchers to better design their research and make new contributions to existing fields of knowledge. There are several types of literature review studies, including: (1) Narrative review: namely a type of literature review study that is descriptive in nature and does not involve the use of statistical methods. Narrative reviews focus on collecting, summarizing, and synthesizing existing research results. (2) Systematic review: namely a type of literature review study that involves systematic and structured methods for collecting, analyzing and synthesizing relevant research results. Systematic reviews are carried out with the aim of producing more accurate and reliable conclusions. (3) Meta-analysis: namely a type of literature review study that involves the use of statistical methods to combine the results of different studies and produce more robust effect estimates. Literature review studies can be conducted in various fields of science and are used for various purposes, such as to develop understanding of a topic, obtain empirical evidence that supports a hypothesis or theory, or identify research needs that are still unmet.

Previous research on DAR in banking continues to develop along with the increasing importance of this ratio in analyzing banking financial health. Several recent studies have revealed several important findings regarding the use of DAR in banking. First, one study shows that the DAR ratio can influence bank profitability. The research results show that a higher DAR ratio has a negative impact on bank profitability. However, this research also shows that this negative impact can be compensated for by higher levels of liquidity and better asset quality. Second, other research shows that the DAR ratio can also influence systemic risk in banking. The research results show that a higher DAR ratio can increase systemic risk in banking. However, this research also shows that banks that have better portfolio diversification can reduce the negative impact of a higher DAR ratio. Third, other research shows that the DAR ratio can influence bank performance in facing a financial crisis. Research results show that banks that have a lower DAR ratio tend to have better performance in facing the financial crisis. These studies show that the use of the DAR ratio in banking has a significant influence on banking financial health. The results of this research can be used by supervisors and banks to improve risk management and make better decisions in banking financial management.

The aim of this research is to map research topics around DAR in Banking using: (1) the VOSviewer bibliometric method to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) literature study review to analyze, identify and review articles from the accredited national journal Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding DAR. This can be a reference for other researchers who wish to research DAR.

The implication and contribution of this research is to map research topics regarding the DAR ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The research object is Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles about DAR in Sharia and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection comes from search for Sinta accredited national journals via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and software Perish/Harzing. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel software, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the keyword " Debt to Asset Ratio " and " DAR" throughout the year; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding DAR using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on publication year; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and journal publication trends around DAR using the VOSviewer algorithm software (Visualization of Similarities) based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics around DAR using a literature review study.

Results and Discussion

Mapping Distribution of Scientific Publications regarding Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

There are 235 national journals accredited by Sinta based on the results of data collection using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop originating from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) and Perish/Harzing software during the period 2012 to 2022. The results are as follows:

Journal publication data regarding Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR) by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
2012	1	2016	6	2020	32
2013	5	2017	7	2021	60
2014	2	2018	15	2022	77
2015	1	2019	29		

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

VOSviewer Bibliometric Study Mapping of Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Search results for articles on software Perish/Harzing are exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, then input and analyzed using VOSviewer software. The results are as follows:

		method, data analysis technique, data collection technique, data processing, documentation technique, earnings per share, eps, financial performance, growth, hypothesis test, Indonesian stock exchange, inventory turnover, investor, manufacturing company, partial test, influence of return, price, r square, rest, share price, size, stock price, test result, variation.
5	22	asset and debt ratio, capital structure, decision, der, equity ratio to return, f table, influence, level, net profit, performance, problem, profit, ratio, relationship, research method, roe, service, significant influence, spss version, total asset ratio.
6	8	beverage company, food, Indonesia stock exchange, quantitative method, receivable turnover, significant negative effect, tattoos, total asset turnover.

Mapping Literature Review Study regarding the Influence of Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR) on Sharia and Conventional Banking

literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 28 influences of DAR on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

(1) Audit Delay. The higher the DAR ratio, the more likely the company will experience financial problems, which can lengthen the audit time. This happens because companies with a high DAR ratio tend to have a higher level of financial risk and auditors need to carry out more thorough examinations to ensure the correctness of the financial statements. Therefore, the higher the DAR ratio, the greater the possibility of audit delays.

(2) Tax aggressiveness. The DAR ratio can influence tax aggressiveness, namely the company's strategy in minimizing their tax burden. Companies with a high DAR ratio tend to use debt as a source of funding, which can generate interest that can be deducted from company income in tax calculations. Therefore, companies with a high DAR ratio tend to have a higher tendency to use tax aggressiveness strategies.

(3) Beta of sharia shares. The higher the DAR ratio, the more likely the company is to experience high financial risk, which can cause share price volatility. Therefore, companies with a high DAR ratio tend to have a higher stock beta.

(4) Cash holding. Companies with a high DAR ratio tend to experience dependence on debt as a source of funding, which can cause cash shortages. Therefore, companies with a high DAR ratio tend to have lower cash holdings, which can make it difficult for them to meet financial obligations and experience liquidity difficulties.

(5) Cost Stickiness. DAR can affect Cost Stickiness in banking, because the higher the debt ratio, the more difficult it is for the bank to adjust its operational costs to changes in income. Therefore, the higher the DAR, the higher the possibility of cost stickiness in banking.

(6) Dividend Payout Ratio/DPR. DAR can influence DPR on banks, because the higher the debt ratio, the more difficult it is for banks to pay dividends. Banks may need to retain profits to pay their debts, thereby reducing the bank's ability to pay dividends. Therefore, the higher the DAR, the lower the probability of DPR on banking.

(7) Effective Tax Rate/ETR. DAR can affect ETR in banking, because the higher the debt ratio, the higher the interest burden that must be paid by the bank. Interest expenses can be deducted from income before being taxed, thereby reducing the amount of tax that must be paid by the bank. Therefore, the higher the DAR, the lower the ETR in banking.

(8) Earnings Per Share/EPS. DAR can affect EPS in banking, because the higher the debt ratio, the higher the interest costs that must be paid by the bank.

Interest expense can reduce the net income available to divide by the number of shares outstanding, thereby reducing EPS. Therefore, the higher the DAR, the lower the EPS in banking.

(9) Financial Distress. A high DAR can indicate high debt levels and a greater risk of bankruptcy. Therefore, banks with high DAR are more vulnerable to experiencing financial distress when adverse situations occur, such as a decrease in interest rates or a decline in asset quality. Financial distress can result in the inability of banks to fulfill their financial obligations, such as paying interest or principal, and could potentially result in liquidation or restructuring.

(10) Share price. A high DAR can cause investors to worry about a company's ability to pay back its debt and affect the company's share price. When investors perceive that a company has a higher risk of bankruptcy, the company's stock price tends to decrease. Therefore, companies with high DAR may experience downward pressure on share prices.

(11) Company performance. High DAR can affect company performance. Too much debt can burden a company's cash flow and affect the company's ability to grow its business. In addition, banks with high DAR may have higher debt costs, which can reduce the company's net profit. Therefore, high DAR can reduce company performance.

(12) Dividend policy. A high DAR can influence a company's dividend policy. When a company has high debt, most of its net profits can be used to pay interest and principal on debt, leaving little or no remaining profits to distribute as dividends to shareholders. Therefore, companies with high DAR may have a lower dividend policy.

(13) Net profit. In the short term, an increase in DAR can increase a company's net profit, because the company can use the money borrowed to finance investments that can generate profits. However, in the long term, a high DAR ratio can worsen net income because interest and other costs associated with debt will become a burden for the company.

(14) Company value. In the short term, an increase in DAR can increase company value, because the company can use the money borrowed to make investments that can increase company value. However, in the long term, an increase in the DAR ratio can reduce company value due to the potential for greater financial risk.

(15) Net Income Growth. A decrease in DAR can increase net profit growth because the company will have more capital to invest. However, a company must manage its debt wisely to ensure that its investments can generate sufficient profits to compensate for the cost of debt.

(16) Net Profit Margin/NPM. In the short term, increasing DAR can increase NPM because companies can use the money borrowed to finance investments that can increase revenue and reduce operational costs. However, in the long term, an increase in the DAR ratio can reduce NPM because interest and other costs associated with debt will become a burden for the company.

(17) Corporate income tax payable by the company. DAR can affect the corporate income tax a company owes. The higher the DAR ratio, the more interest the company must pay to finance its debt. This causes higher interest expenses on the company's income statement. Thus, corporate corporate income tax tends to be lower because interest expenses can be deducted from taxable income.

(18) Tax avoidance. Banking companies may try to reduce tax payments by avoiding taxes. A high DAR ratio can provide incentives for companies to avoid taxes by moving profits to countries or regions with lower tax rates. So, the higher the DAR ratio, the greater the possibility that the company will avoid tax.

(19) Changes in profit. The DAR ratio can influence changes in company profits. The higher the DAR ratio, the higher the company's leverage level. When

interest rates rise, the interest expense that companies have to pay will also increase. This can reduce company profits because the income earned is not enough to cover the increasing interest costs.

(20) Profit growth. The level of the DAR ratio can also influence the company's profit growth. If a company has a low DAR ratio, then the company's ability to obtain additional funding to develop its business will be greater. However, if the company has a high DAR ratio, then the company's ability to obtain additional funding will be more limited. Thus, the company's profit growth can be hampered by a high DAR ratio.

(21) Profit persistence. Profit persistence refers to a company's ability to maintain its financial performance over time. DAR can influence the persistence of profits in banking because the higher the DAR, the greater the financial risk faced by the company. This financial risk can affect the company's ability to maintain its performance in the long term, so that it can affect profit persistence.

(22) Changes in remaining operating results. Changes in residual operating results refer to changes that occur in a company's profits after deducting operational costs. DAR can influence changes in residual operating results in banking because the higher the DAR, the greater the interest expense that must be paid by the company. This interest expense can affect the remaining business results because the greater the interest expense, the smaller the remaining business results available.

(23) Member economy. DAR can affect the economy of banking members because the higher the DAR, the greater the financial risk faced by the company. High financial risks can affect a company's ability to provide loans to members and can also affect the stability of the banking sector as a whole.

(24) Price Book Value/PBV. PBV refers to the comparison between the company's share price and the book value of the company's shares. DAR can influence PBV in banking because the higher the DAR, the greater the financial risk faced by the company. High financial risk can affect investors' perceptions of the company, so that it can affect PBV.

(25) Return On Assets/ROA. DAR can influence ROA in banking because the higher this ratio, the greater the financial risk faced by the company. This can reduce the company's ability to generate profits from its assets, which can affect ROA.

(26) Return On Equity/ROE. DAR can affect ROE in banking because the higher this ratio, the greater the financial risk faced by the company. This can reduce the company's ability to generate profits from its equity, which can affect ROE.

(27) Return Share. DAR can influence the return share in banking because the higher this ratio, the greater the financial risk faced by the company. This can affect the company's financial performance and its impact on share prices and dividends distributed to shareholders.

(28) Stock returns. DAR can influence stock returns in banking because the higher this ratio, the greater the financial risk faced by the company. This can influence investors' perceptions of the company and its share price.

Mapping Literature Review Study regarding Determinant Variables Debt to Asset Ratio/DAR in Sharia and Conventional Banking

literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 12 determinant variables of DAR in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

(1) Asset Growth. Increasing asset growth in banking will increase banking's ability to generate income through credit and investment activities. However, if asset growth is not balanced with sufficient income growth, banks will experience a decline in profits and possibly an increase in risk levels. This may lead to an

increase in DAR as rapid asset growth may require more loans and financial obligations.

(2) Operational Costs to Operational Income/BOPO. The higher the BOPO ratio, the higher the banking operational costs relative to operating income. If BOPO continues to increase without being balanced by an increase in operational income, banks will experience a decrease in profits and possibly an increase in risk levels. This condition can cause an increase in DAR because high operational costs can reduce income and increase financial obligations.

(3) Current Ratio. The higher the Current Ratio, the more current assets are available to meet short-term obligations. If a bank has a high Current Ratio, the possibility of experiencing short-term liquidity shortages will be lower, so that banks do not need to take out loans or other financial obligations to fulfill short-term obligations. This can help reduce DAR.

(4) Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR. The higher the LDR, the higher the banking risk, because more loans are given compared to the amount of funds received from deposits. If LDR continues to increase without being matched by sufficient growth in deposits, banks may need to obtain funds from other sources such as loans or other financial obligations. This can lead to an increase in DAR as more financial obligations need to be met.

(5) Non Performing Loans/NPL. The higher the NPL level at a bank, the more likely it is that the bank will experience losses and it will be difficult to pay debts. Therefore, banks with high NPL levels tend to have high DAR because they have to take on more debt to finance these losses.

(6) Non-Debt Tax Shield. If a company has a high NDTs, then the company tends to use internal funds to finance its operational activities, and therefore will have a lower DAR.

(7) Price Book Value/PBV. The higher the PBV, the higher the company's market value compared to its book value, and therefore the company tends to have a high equity value. Banks with high PBV tend to have low DAR because they can raise additional capital through issuing shares, and do not need to take on too much debt.

(8) Return On Assets/ROA. The higher the ROA, the better the company's financial performance and therefore the company tends to have a high equity value. Banks with high ROA tend to have low DAR because they can raise additional capital through issuing shares, and do not need to take on too much debt.

(9) Return On Equity/ROE. The higher the ROE of a company, the more efficient the company is in managing its capital. In terms of banking, ROE can also indicate the level of risk taken by the bank in managing capital. If ROE is high, then banks tend to take greater risks in seeking profits, including increasing leverage and debt.

(10) Asset structure. Asset structure also influences DAR in banking. Banks that have more liquid assets, such as cash and securities, tend to have lower DAR. In contrast, banks that have more illiquid assets, such as loans and credit, tend to have higher DAR. Therefore, the different asset structures in each bank will affect its DAR.

(11) Time Interest Earned. The higher the TIE, the more capable the company is of paying interest on its debt and the lower the possibility of the company experiencing financial difficulties resulting in high debt dependence. Therefore, banks with high TIE tend to have lower DAR.

(12) Company size. Company size can influence banking DAR. Larger companies tend to have access to greater funding sources and better risk diversification. Thus, larger banks tend to have lower DAR.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, based on mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding the Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR) ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking during the period 2012 to 2022, it shows a significant increase from year to year. The total number of publications is 235 research articles, which come from accredited national journals, Sinta. Second, based on the VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, the network visualization results around the DAR ratio Sharia and Conventional Banking is divided into 6 clusters and 171 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 41 topics, cluster 2 consists of 36 topics, cluster 3 consists of 35 topics, cluster 4 consists of 29 topics, cluster 5 consists of 22 topics, and cluster 6 consists of 8 topics. Third, based on mapping literature review studies, there are 28 topics related to the influence of the DAR ratio on banking, namely: audit delay, tax aggressiveness, sharia share beta, cash holding, cost stickiness, Dividend Payout Ratio/DPR, Effective Tax Rate/ETR, Earning Per Share/EPS, Financial Distress, price shares, company performance, dividend policy, net profit, company value, Net Income Growth, Net Profit Margin/NPM, corporate income tax payable by the company, tax avoidance, changes in profits, profit growth, profit persistence, changes in residual business results, members' economy, Price Book Value/PBV, Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, Return Share, and Return on shares. And there are 12 topics related to the determinants of the DAR ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: Asset Growth, Operational Costs to Operating Income/BOPO, Current Ratio, Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR, Non Performing Loan/NPL, Non Debt Tax Shield, Price Book Value/PBV, Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, asset structure, Time Interest Earned, and company size.

Suggestion

It is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, both from national accredited journals Sinta and international journals indexed by Scopus, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer time span for research data so that it can following research results were obtained: first, it is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization. Second, the results of the literature review can be explained in a more complex way.

References

- Abidin, U. A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Third-Party Fund (DPK) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117572>
- Aini, A. P. N., Salsabilla, L. Z., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Compilation of Sharia Economic Law (KHES): Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117521>
- Aini, A. P. N., Salsabilla, L. Z., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Kompilasi Hukum Ekonomi Syariah (KHES): Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078577>
- Al-Fattah, M. F., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Islamic and Conventional Mutual Funds (Reksa Dana): Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117306>
- Al-Fattah, M. F., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Reksa Dana Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik*

VOSviewer. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078579>

- Al-Ghozy, H. R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Musaqah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117769>
- Amaliani, A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Income Smoothing (Perataan Laba) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078569>
- Amaliani, A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Income Smoothing on Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions: Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117537>
- Amin, S. M. M., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Garansi pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077304>
- Amin, S. M. M., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Guarantees on Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117749>
- Andresta, T., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Muamalat Indonesia: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117698>
- Andresta, T., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Muamalat Indonesia: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077344>
- Anggreni, L. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *National Sharia Arbitration Agency (BASYARNAS): Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117655>
- Baranuri, M. Y., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Ijarah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117783>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Akad Mudharabah Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *J-EBIS (Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Islam)*, 7(1), 43–68. <https://doi.org/10.32505/j-ebis.v7i1.3895>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Akad Musyarakah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JESI (Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah Indonesia)*, 12(1), 25–36. [https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12\(1\).25-36](https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12(1).25-36)
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Bibliometric And Literature Review Of Financing Risk In Islamic Banking. *JPS (Jurnal Perbankan Syariah)*, 4(1), 79–97. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.46367/jps.v4i1.1031>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Risiko Operasional pada Industri Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Ekonomi Islam*, 14(2), 158–174.

<https://doi.org/10.22236/jei.v14i2.11121>

- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Risiko Reputasi pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Al-Masraf: Jurnal Lembaga Keuangan Dan Perbankan*, 8(1), 94–113. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.15548/al-masraf.v8i1.425>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Risiko Kredit pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BANCO: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 5(1), 20–34. <https://doi.org/10.35905/banco.v5i1.4987>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Research Mapping on Credit Risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking. *AL-INFAQ: Jurnal Ekonomi Islam*, 14(1), 73–86. <https://doi.org/10.32507/ajei.v14i1.1862>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2022). Research Mapping of Musyarakah Contracts in Islamic Financial Institutions: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review. *Maliki Islamic Economics Journal*, 2(2), 76–94. <https://doi.org/10.18860/miec.v2i2.17199>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Danamon Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117751>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Danamon Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077292>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117611>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Cash Ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117607>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117603>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Current Ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117601>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117564>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Dividend Per Share in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117548>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Economic Value Added (EVA) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117545>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Financial Value Added (FVA) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer*

- Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117539>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Financing Risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117292>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Jualah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117779>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Mapping Research on the Ratio of Operating Costs to Operating Income (BOPO) in Sharia and Conventional Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117623>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Net Operating Margin (NOM) on Islamic Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117324>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Net Profit Margin (NPM) Ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117320>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Non Performing Financing (NPF) on Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117318>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Biaya Operasional terhadap Pendapatan Operasional (BOPO) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JAF (Journal of Accounting and Finance)*, 7(1), 34–48. <https://doi.org/10.25124/jaf.v7i1.5995>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JAFTA (Journal of Accounting, Finance, Taxation & Auditing)*, 4(2), 32–53. <https://doi.org/10.28932/jafta.v4i2.7650>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Per Share (DPS) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Al-Mal: Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Keuangan Islam*, 4(1), 109–126. <https://doi.org/10.24042/al-mal.v4i01.16760>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Financial Value Added (FVA) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BJRM (Bongaya Journal of Research in Management)*, 6(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.37888/bjrm.v6i2>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Net Operating Margin (NOM) pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Ecobankers: Journal of Economy and Banking*, 4(2), 84–94. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8323115>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio On Investment (ROI) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi

- Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Kompetensi (Competence: Journal of Management Studies)*, 17(1), 66–82. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21107/kompetensi.v17i1.20002>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Total Asset Turnover (TATO) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Manajemen*, 20(2), 40–53. <https://doi.org/10.36406/jam.v20i2.975>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pengaruh Book Value per Share (BVS) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Islamic Economics and Business Review*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185250>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Reputation Risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117288>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Research Mapping the Operating Profit Margin (OPM) Ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117316>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Return On Investment (ROI) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117286>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Sharf on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117759>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *The Influence of Book Value per Share (BVS) on Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117619>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Total Asset Turnover (TATO) on Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10142629>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Working Capital Turnover (WCT) Ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117154>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Dewi, N. D. T., & Abidin, U. A. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dana Pihak Ketiga (DPK) Pada Perbankan Syariah Dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *Syjar Iqtishadi: Journal of Islamic Economics, Finance and Banking*, 7(1), 25–44. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.35448/jiec.v7i1.19887>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Saputra, H. M. G. A., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Koperasi Jasa Keuangan Syariah (KJKS): Studi Bibliometrik VOS viewer dan Literature Review. *EL MUDHORIB: Jurnal Kajian Ekonomi Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 3(2), 131–148. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185180>
- Cahyaningrum, D., Hariyono, H. N. M., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Guarantees/Collateral in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions: Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117529>

- Cahyaningrum, D., Hariyono, H. N. M., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Jaminan/Agunan pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078573>
- Dewi, N. D. T., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). *The Influence of Macroeconomic Variables: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117329>
- Dewi, N. D. T., Ibad, N. N., Pratopo, G., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Manajemen Zakat Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer Dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomika Dan Bisnis Islam*, 6(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.26740/jekobi.v6n1.p1-20>
- Elkhori, N. E. M., Safira, W. I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Denda pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078519>
- Emiliani, E., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Hawala on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117785>
- Faiz, M. W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Safe Deposit Box pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078581>
- Fajaryati, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Mega Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117747>
- Fajaryati, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Mega Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077317>
- Farida, M., Andrini, H. L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Subrogasi pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078583>
- Farida, M., Andrini, H. L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Subrogation in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions: Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117160>
- Fauzan, I. F. M., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank OCBC NISP Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117745>
- Febrian, J., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). *Pengaruh Pengetahuan, Kepercayaan, Produk, Pelayanan, dan Religiusitas terhadap Minat Menabung*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117278>
- Febrian, J., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). The Effect of Knowledge, Trust, Products, Services and Religiosity on Interest in Saving. *The 9th International Conference of Islamic Economics and Business (ICONIES 2023)*, 85–96. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037033>

- Febriyanti, R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and Bibliometrics VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117743>
- Febriyanti, R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Panin Dubai Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077588>
- Fikri, U. A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Pembangunan Daerah (BPD) Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077610>
- Fikri, U. A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Sharia and Conventional Regional Development Banks (BPD): Mapping Research Topics using Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117690>
- Gozali, M., Saputra, M. A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *The Influence of Return On Equity (ROE) in Islamic Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117294>
- Gozali, M., Saputra, M. A., Dewi, N. D. T., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Variabel Determinan Return On Equity (ROE) pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *IDEI: Jurnal Ekonomi & Bisnis*, 4(1), 34–47. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.38076/ideijeb.v4i1.151>
- Hidayat, R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Victoria Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117712>
- Hidayat, R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Victoria Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078459>
- Ibad, N. N., Pratopo, G., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Zakah Management in Islamic Financial Institutions: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117328>
- Laksana, E. Y., Rusydi, F. N., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) in Islamic Financial Institutions: Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117554>
- Laksana, Y. E., Rusydi, F. N., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Dewan Pengawas Syariah (DPS) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078565>
- Mawardi, M. I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Sharia and Conventional National Pension Savings Bank (BTPN): Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117662>
- Muna, R. M., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Syariah Indonesia (BSI): Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117678>
- Muna, R. M., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Syariah Indonesia*

- (BSI): *Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078436>
- Nursaputri, D. D., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Muzara'ah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117767>
- Panatagama, A. R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Wakalah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117755>
- Prayogi, A. H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Permata Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117740>
- Prayogi, A. H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Permata Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077628>
- Putri, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Bukopin Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117655>
- Qudratullah, M. Q., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Murabaha on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117771>
- Rahmawati, L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Tabungan Negara (BTN) Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117670>
- Ratnasari, A. D., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Rahn (Pawn) on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117763>
- Rofiah, A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Wadi'ah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117757>
- Rofika, H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Maybank Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117627>
- Rofika, H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Maybank Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomi: Journal of Economic*, 14(1), 28–39. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.47007/jeko.v14i01.6463>
- Rohimah, W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank CIMB Niaga Sharia and Conventional on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117629>
- Rohimah, W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik

- VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Perbankan*, Vol 5, No 1 (2023): JEMPER Januari-Juni, 30–40. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185264>
- Rohmah, R. A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *The Application of Financial Accounting Standard Statements (PSAK) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117314>
- Rohmandika, M. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Variabel Determinan Return On Asset pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Eco-Iqtishodi: Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Dan Keuangan Syariah*, 5(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.32670/ecoiqtishodi.v5i1.3607>
- Rohmandika, M. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Research Mapping around the Determinant Variables of Return on Assets (ROA) in Islamic Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117298>
- Saputra, H. M. G. A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Sharia Financial Services Cooperatives (KJKS): Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117332>
- Saputri, M. I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Internet Banking in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117533>
- Sufia, I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Salam on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117761>
- Suwandini, F. K. T., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Islamic Rural Banks (BPRS): Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometric*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117684>
- Syarifah, H. L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Qard on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117765>
- Ummah, F. K., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Fatwa Dewan Syariah Nasional Majelis Ulama Indonesia (DSN-MUI) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078567>
- Wulandari, D. R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Central Asia (BCA) Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and Bibliometrics VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117704>
- Wulandari, D. R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Central Asia (BCA) Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10075718>
- Zahro, T. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Istisna' on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117781>

